

A METHOD FOR CALCULATING ABSOLUTE SINGLE ELECTRODE POTENTIAL

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A new method has been developed depending upon the maximum heat that could be done in passing from one state to the other or *vice versa*, for calculating absolute single electrode potential.

Every electrode process is an oxidation-reduction process, since it involves gain or loss of electrons by atoms or ions and can be represented by the equation,

Our problem is to find out the maximum work that could be done in passing from state A to state B⁺ or *vice versa*. If this work is performed electrically, we get the desired e.m.f. Thus, when *n* electrons are involved,

$$enV = -\Delta F = kT \ln K = kT \ln [ne] + kT \ln \frac{[B^+]}{[A]}$$

$$\text{or } V = \frac{kT}{ne} \ln [ne] + \frac{kT}{ne} \ln \frac{[B^+]}{[A]}$$

= V_0 , when the activities of B⁺ and A are unity.

Here, V_0 = the standard absolute electrode potential,

K = the equilibrium constant,

ΔF = the maximum work done upon the system *i.e.*, the gain in free energy,

e = the electronic charge,

n = the number of electrons transferred, and

V = the absolute electrode potential.

Let us consider the following cases

Case I.—Here both Fe^{++} and Fe^{+++} ions are in solution and the process of transformation is simply the transference of one electron from Fe^{++} . Let the work, to be done on the system, to extract one electron from Fe^{++} be μJ , electron volts. When there is a suitable indifferent electrode in the medium, e. g., Pt, this work is converted into electrical work by the passage of the liberated electron which therefore gives an e. m. f. equal to μJ , volts. The work is done upon the system by the oxidising agent and the electrode here acts only as a channel for the passage of electrons. The e. m. f. therefore ought not to depend on the nature of the electrode provided that no chemical reaction takes place between the electrode and the medium.

Table I, taken from Gurney ("Ions in Solution", Cambridge University Press, 1936, pp. 117-178), give the ' μJ_m ' values for several such red-ox systems, as well as their standard potentials referred to the hydrogen electrode. Since μJ_m is the absolute potential of the system, we easily get the absolute potential of the hydrogen electrode from their relative values. It will be noted that the difference of J values is the same as that in the relative scale.

TABLE I

System.	' μJ_m ' electron.	Standard red-ox potentials in aq. soln. referred to the H-electrode.	Absolute potential of the H-electrode.
$\text{Cr}^{++} \rightleftharpoons \text{Cr}^{+++}$	3.67 volts	-0.4 volt	4.07 volts
$\text{Ti}^{++} \rightleftharpoons \text{Ti}^{+++}$	4.4	+0.37	4.03
$\text{Fe}^{++} \rightleftharpoons \text{Fe}^{+++}$	4.8	+0.75	4.05
$\text{Ce}^{+++} \rightleftharpoons \text{Ce}^{++++}$	5.6	+1.55	4.05
$\text{Co}^{++} \rightleftharpoons \text{Co}^{+++}$	5.9	+1.82	4.08

Case II.—The reaction is equivalent to the transference of a silver atom (*i.e.* Ag^+ ion core plus an electron) from the metallic lattice to the solution in the ionic form. The energy difference between the two states can be calculated by considering the following mechanism. First the silver atom is evaporated from the lattice which would require the energy of sublimation, S . The vaporised atom is then ionised and finally solvated. The total energy required is $S+I-W$, where I and W are ionisation and solvation energies. When all of them are expressed in electron volts, the absolute standard electrode potential of the system is given by*,

$$V_0 = S + I - W.$$

Gurney (*ibid.*, Chap. XIV, p. 202) has given the values of heat of solvation for various ions as well as the relation between the heat of solvation and solvation energies. Table II gives the absolute potential of the hydrogen electrode calculated from this picture.

* As the entropies of Ag^+ ions in the metallic lattice and in the solution are different, the whole of this amount of energy could not be converted into useful work. The potential, in that case, would be given by Gibbs-Helmholtz relation.

TABLE II

System.	Absolute values of e m.f. ($S+I-W$).	Standard electrode potential referred to H-electrode.	Absolute pot. of the H-electrode.
Ag $\begin{array}{c} \rightarrow \\ \leftarrow \end{array}$ Ag ⁺	(2.90 + 7.54 - 5.5) = 4.94 volts	+0.798 volt	4.142 volts
K $\begin{array}{c} \rightarrow \\ \leftarrow \end{array}$ K ⁺	(0.94 + 4.12 - 4.1) = 1.16	-2.924	4.084
Rb $\begin{array}{c} \rightarrow \\ \leftarrow \end{array}$ Rb ⁺	(0.87 + 4.16 - 3.8) = 1.23	-2.926	4.156

Case III.—The process consists in tearing away a chlorine atom from the AgCl lattice, dissociating the resulting chlorine molecule, ionising a chlorine atom and finally passing the anion into solution. If Q be the heat of formation† of AgCl from Ag and Cl₂ molecules; D , the dissociation energy of Cl₂ molecules; I , the electron affinity of the chlorine atom; W , the solvation energy of the Cl⁻ ion, then the energy gained is

$$\frac{1}{2}Q + \frac{1}{2}D - I - W = (1.20 + 1.23 - 3.8 - 2.8) \text{ e.v.} = -4.17 \text{ e.v.}$$

Since here the anion is transferred, the absolute potential of the electrode is +4.17 volts. Standard potential of AgCl-Cl⁻ electrode is +0.22 volt. Hence, the absolute potential of the hydrogen electrode is +3.97 volts.

Case IV.—Here the equilibrium is between the hydrogen atom and the hydrogen ion in the solution. Hence the energy required to take one hydrogen atom from the gaseous state to the solution in the ionic form is

$$\left(\frac{1}{2}D + I - W\right) = (2.24 + 13.53 - 12.0) = 3.77 \text{ e.v.}$$

where D is the dissociation energy and I , the ionisation energy. Now, if we add to this the energy of desorption of hydrogen molecules from the surface of the platinum black, about 0.35 electron volt per atom of hydrogen*, we get the value of absolute potential of the hydrogen electrode as 4.12 volts.

The kinetic picture would be the same as that visualised by Gurney (*loc. cit.*, pp. 85-88). When a metal is dipped into the solution containing its ions, either the metal ions will go into solution or the ions in the solution will be deposited on the surface of the lattice depending on their relative energies of solution and deposition until a potential V is set up on the surface of the metal which prevents further solution or deposition. In other words, at the equilibrium stage, the number of ions passing into solution must be equal to the number of ions deposited.

† I have again assumed that this energy is converted not into heat but into useful work. Otherwise, the energy difference between any two states and the difference in their free energies would, in all cases, be related by Gibbs-Helmholtz equation and taking the experimentally determined values of dV/dT we could easily calculate the value of V .

* The heat of desorption of molecular hydrogen is known only approximately and as given by Glasstone ("Recent Advances in Physical Chemistry", J.A. Churchill Ltd., 1936, p. 43) it lies between -10,000 and -25,000 cal. per mole.

Now, the fraction of the total number of ions on the surface of the lattice having energies greater than $U_m - ne\psi$ is given by $\int_0^{\alpha} e^{-\frac{U-U_m+ne\psi}{kT}} dU$ where U_m is the minimum energy required to take an ion out of the lattice. For the ions in solution the number is given by $\int_0^{\alpha} e^{-\frac{U-W}{kT}} dU$. The probability of a metallic ion going into solution will depend on the number of solvent molecules N_s and that of ions in solution to deposit, on the number of solute particles N . Hence at equilibrium

$$N_s \int_0^{\alpha} e^{-\frac{U-U_m+ne\psi}{kT}} dU = N \int_0^{\alpha} e^{-\frac{U-W}{kT}} dU$$

or, $V = + \frac{U_m - W}{ne} + \frac{kT}{ne} \ln C$ where $C = \frac{N}{N_s}$

$$\text{or } V = V_0 + \frac{kT}{ne} \ln a,$$

if we substitute the concentration by the activity which depends on the effective number of solute molecules colliding on the surface of the metal.

Considering the widely different mechanisms employed and the fact that none too accurate values of relevant data are available the agreement between the different cases seems striking. In case I both the components (Fe^{++} and Fe^{+++}) are in the same phase and the maximum work obtained here gives directly the changes in free energy. The most probable value of the absolute potential of the hydrogen electrode would therefore be in the neighbourhood of 4.05 volts.